

Dyes Derived from Acetylene Dicarboxylic Acid.

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In the light of 'A theory of colour on the basis of molecular strain' advanced by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 99), substances containing acetylenic linkages should produce greater absorption of light in the higher wave lengths and consequently should be more deeply coloured than those containing ethylenic linkages by virtue of the former possessing triple bonds in place of the double bonds of the latter. A comparison of the absorption maxima of some well known ethylenic and acetylenic compounds brings out this fact very clearly. Thus:

Name of the compound.	Absorption maxima	Name.	Absorption maxima.
Ethylene	2440	Elaidic acid	2500
Acetylene	2470	Stearolic acid	2640
Styrene	2730	Diphenyldiethylene	3400
Phenylacetylene	2740	Diphenyldiacetylene	3630
Cinnamic acid	2800	Diiodo-ethylene	2860
Phenylpropionic acid	2820	Diiodo-acetylene	2940
Stilbene	2860		
Tolane	3030		

All the compounds mentioned above being colourless, their absorption bands lie in the ultra-violet region of the spectrum. Consequently their determination is a matter of considerable difficulty, and their position is also found to change slightly with change in conditions and solvents in which they are examined. On account of this it was thought that if some dyestuffs could be prepared containing acetylenic linkages in their molecules, they could be easily compared with their ethylenic analogues by direct determination of their absorption spectra by means of a high dispersion glass spectrograph either by eye observation or by photographic methods. Selection of an appropriate starting material was not particularly easy on account of the great

paucity of data available in literature with regard to acetylenic compounds and acetylene dicarboxylic acid was selected for this purpose.

Acetylene dicarboxylic acid is very unstable in the ordinary sense, since when heated to its temperature of fusion, *i.e.*, 178°, it loses carbon dioxide progressively and gets converted first into propargylic acid and finally into acetylene. It does not give any anhydride under ordinary conditions, since most of the inorganic dehydrating agents like sulphuric acid, zinc chloride, hydrogen chloride, etc., employed for the production of anhydrides from dibasic acids, decompose it into carbon dioxide and propargylic acid. By heating with acetic anhydride, the acid gets converted into acetoxy-maleic anhydride (I). Acetyl chloride also gives the same product under identical conditions.

Since the acid does not form an anhydride under the usual conditions, it was at first thought that the production of the pyronine dyestuffs from the acid, which require the intermediate formation of the anhydride, would not be feasible, but as the result of trial experiments it was found that pyronine dyestuffs are quite readily formed from acetylene dicarboxylic acid by condensation with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds in the normal manner. Consequently the only hypothesis that can be advanced to explain this interesting phenomenon is that acetylene dicarboxylic acid does form an anhydride like maleic and succinic acids, but under ordinary conditions, the anhydride is very unstable and undergoes decomposition as soon as it is formed. If, however, substances are simultaneously present with which the anhydride can undergo condensation, it reacts with them as soon as it is formed with production of stable condensation products.

By analogy with dyes derived from citraconic acid (Dhar and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 254) it is found that dyes derived from acetylene dicarboxylic acid also possess the same skeleton structure with the exception that the latter possess a triple bond in place of the double bond of the former. Consequently it can be expected that dyes derived from acetylene dicarboxylic acid will be more deeply coloured than the corresponding dyes derived from citraconic acid. This expectation with regard to these dyestuffs has been realised and

on systematic comparison it has been found that they are more deeply coloured and more absorptive than the corresponding dyes derived from citraconic, itaconic or maleic acid. This will be quite evident from the tables of absorption maxima given at the end of the paper.

The following aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds have been condensed with acetylene dicarboxylic acid and the corresponding dyestuffs obtained: phenol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol, orcinol, *m*-dimethylamidophenol, *m*-diethylamidophenol and *m*-phenylenediamine. The compound with resorcinol has also been brominated and the corresponding tetrabromo derivative prepared. The triple bond has been found to be unattacked during the process.

Condensation was not found to take place in the following cases: *o*-, and *p*-cresol, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-xylenols and *m*-amidophenol. In the case of catechol and pyrogallol, although condensation had apparently occurred, yet the products could not be obtained in a state of sufficient purity for further examination or analysis.

Although condensations took place without the use of any condensing agent, yet the employment of a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid and in some cases, tin tetrachloride, was found to be beneficial in producing greater yield of the dyestuffs. Nevertheless it was found, however, that the yields obtained were very unsatisfactory on account of the formation of many by-products, and a considerable loss of the starting materials occurred during the condensation process. With the exception of the phenol compound, all the rest of the dyestuffs are strongly fluorescent in solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenol-acetylenein.—A mixture of acetylene dicarboxylic acid (2.1 g.), phenol (6 g.) and tin tetrachloride (15 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 110-120° for 15 hours. The melt on cooling was poured into water and the excess of phenol distilled off in steam. The residue was extracted with concentrated ammonia, precipitated with hydrochloric acid and the process repeated a number of times. The brown product was finally purified by extraction with ether and crystallisation from the same solvent. It is a brownish yellow micro-crystalline substance, which shrinks at 115° and melts at 119-120° (decomp.). It is readily soluble in alcohol to a pink solution. In acetone, glacial acetic acid and ether a bright yellow solution is obtained. It is

insoluble in water, chloroform, ligroin, benzene, petroleum ether and carbon disulphide. In dilute alkalis it dissolves with a brilliant pink colour and from the solution it is reprecipitated unchanged by acidification. (Found: C, 72.05; H, 3.82. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 72.18; H, 3.76 per cent).

Resorcinol-acetylenein.—A mixture of acetylene dicarboxylic acid (1.5 g.), resorcinol (4 g.) and two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was heated in an oil-bath at 120-130° for 8 hours. The reaction product was then dissolved in 5% cold caustic soda solution and after filtration it was reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was then dissolved in absolute alcohol and precipitated by dry ether. Finally it was crystallised from absolute alcohol in brown microscopic needles which decomposed at 185°. It dissolves in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid and pyridine forming bright yellow solutions with intense green fluorescence. In dilute caustic alkalis it dissolves with an orange colour and the same bright green fluorescence. (Found: C, 67.67; H, 3.83. $C_{16}H_8O_5$ requires C, 67.77; H, 3.86 per cent).

Tetrabromoresorcinol-acetylenein.—The above compound (0.8 g.) dissolved in alcohol (40 c.c.) was treated with an excess of bromine in the same solvent and the mixture heated under reflux on the water-bath for 3 hours. On the addition of water a dark brown heavy liquid was precipitated which was separated by decantation and washed with mixed solutions of potassium iodide and sodium thiosulphate in order to remove the excess of bromine still present. On treatment of the heavy liquid with cold 2% caustic soda, the greater portion of it dissolved forming a bright pink solution, while a small oily residue remained. The latter on examination was found to be bromoform and the pink solution on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid precipitated the colouring matter in brick-red flocks which were collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in steel-blue needles with a golden metallic lustre. It melts at 115-117° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 53.46. $C_{16}H_6O_5Br_4$ requires Br, 53.51 per cent).

Phloroglucinol-acetylenein was obtained from phloroglucinol and acetylene dicarboxylic acid according to the method described above. The substance crystallises from absolute alcohol in brown microscopic needles which do not melt up to 310°. It dissolves in most of the organic solvents and also in dilute alkalis with a yellowish pink colour. (Found: C, 57.72; H, 3.77. $C_{16}H_8O_7, H_2O$ requires C, 58.09; H, 3.03 per cent).

Orcinol-acetylenein was obtained from orcinol and acetylene-dicarboxylic acid in a similar way to the above. It is a light yellow amorphous powder, m.p. 155-157° (decomp.) and dissolves in most of the organic solvents with a yellow colour and in dilute alkalis with a bright pink colour. The solution in each case has a dark green fluorescence. (Found : C, 69.96; H, 4.08. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 70.13 H, 3.96 per cent).

m-Dimethylamidophenol-acetylenein.—A mixture of acetylene-dicarboxylic acid (2.5 g.), *m*-dimethylamidophenol (6 g.) and 4 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was heated in an oil-bath at 130-140° for 8 hours. The cold melt was extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid and the filtered extract precipitated with dilute sodium carbonate. The pink coloured flocculent mass was filtered off and crystallised from 80% alcohol in fine pink needles, m.p. 126° (decomp.). It is easily soluble in alcohol and acetone, giving pink solutions with strong orange-brown fluorescence. In dilute acids also the same colour and fluorescence are observed. It is moderately soluble in chloroform, pyridine and ethyl acetate but dissolves only slightly in carbon disulphide and ether. It is completely insoluble in water, benzene and petroleum ether. (Found : N, 8.61. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.36 per cent).

m-Diethylamidophenol-acetylenein was prepared from acetylene-dicarboxylic acid and *m*-diethylamidophenol in a similar way to the above. It is a pink substance, having properties very similar to the above mentioned compound, m.p. 109° (decomp.). (Found : N, 7.39. $C_{24}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7.18 per cent).

m-Phenylenediamine-acetylenein.—A mixture of acetylene-dicarboxylic acid (2 g.) and *m*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (4.5 g.) was rapidly melted over a free flame and quickly cooled, the whole operation hardly taking more than 2 minutes. The dark red melt was extracted with absolute alcohol and filtered from the unchanged diamine hydrochloride. The addition of ether to the above filtrate precipitated the dyestuff in bright yellow flocks which were collected and crystallised from 90% alcohol in light brown microscopic needles which decompose without melting at 260°. The constitution of the compound has been assumed to possess an acridine ring structure in accordance with the work of the previous workers in this line (*cf.* Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1102; Sircar and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1285; Dutt, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 2389; 1923, 123, 225; Tewari and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2, 161; 1927, 3, 201; 1928, 4, 59).

DYES DERIVED FROM ACETYLENE DICARBOXYLIC ACID 103

The substance is fairly soluble in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid and pyridine, slightly soluble in ethyl acetate, chloroform and water and completely insoluble in ether, benzene, carbon disulphide, ligroin and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 15.54. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.17 per cent).

Absorption maxima of the acetyleneins and their analogues,

Compound.	Acetylenein.	Malein.	Citraconein.	Itaconein.
Phenol-	5210	...	...	...
Resorcinol-	5180	4890	4940	4880
Tetrabromo resorcinol-	5600	5180	5490	...
<i>m</i> -Diethylamido- phenol-	5670	5400	5560	5470
Phloroglucinol-	5640	...	...	...

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